

The diversity of native plants and their application in environmental education and teaching

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Abstract

Greening campuses is an integral component of creating campus environments. Students can learn about and observe campus plants, and teachers can use the plants as on-site teaching materials. This makes schools ideal for environmental education. This study conducted on-site surveys and analyzed the correlations between campus plant resource factors at 20 elementary schools in the Chiayi area, Taiwan. Elevation, proportion of native plants, species diversity, campus area, and normalized difference vegetation index were the variables considered. There were 150 families, 518 genera, and 770 plant species in total for all campuses, but only 322 (41.47%) species were native. Schools with a high elevation, a small campus area, and a rural location had a significantly greater proportion of native plants on campus and plant species per unit area than schools with other elevations, areas, and locations. The majority of campus plants are ornamental alien species. The lower proportion of native species hinders students' ability to comprehend native and endemic plant species of Taiwan. Going forward, the proportion of native plants planted on campus should be increased progressively, along with the incorporation of these plants into the curriculum, to strengthen administrators' knowledge of campus plant management.

Keywords: campus plants, native species, species diversity

Introduction

Taiwan is an island situated in the middle of the Pacific island chain, off the southeast coast of the

Asian Continent. As a result of the subduction between the Eurasian and Philippine Sea plates, Taiwan's topology is distinguished by its varied terrain and pronounced elevation differences. Its flora ranges from broadleaf forests to alpine tundra, with more than 4,077 vascular plant species, 26% of which are endemic (Huang & Editorial Committee of the Flora of Taiwan, 2003).

Plants in Taiwan can be classified as alien or native based on their origin (Pysek et al., 2004). Native plants are those that originate and occur naturally in a particular region and are unrelated to human activities, whereas alien plants occur due to human intervention or have arrived at a particular region on their own. Schools frequently cultivate plants to improve the local environment or ecology. The overuse of non-native species relative to native species may pose a threat to the campus ecosystem's stability. Alien species, for example, can evolve into invasive species that cause ecological damage (Anderson & Crosby, 2018; Lowe et al., 2000). Resilient alien species may even become a super species (Pal et al., 2019). Increasing biodiversity can increase a region's resistance to invasive species (Downing et al., 2012). School grounds with fewer tree species (low biodiversity) may have a negative impact on the local ecosystem (Carnol et al., 2014). Loss of biodiversity reduces a plant's ability to recover after a major disturbance. Complementarity of niches, which occurs in highly diverse communities, enhances the ecological function (Carvalho et al., 2013). Tree biodiversity influences trophic interactions in a number of positive ways, including increasing the diversity and abundance of trophic levels, whether through mutualism or antagonism, and the redundancy of interaction partners (Fornoff et al., 2019). Given that species interactions improve the resilience of an ecosystem, highly diverse plant communities are more likely to maintain their populations in the face of environmental stressors (Lüscher et al., 2022).

Greening provides educational, aesthetic, and health benefits in addition to its environmental and ecological contributions (Speake et al., 2013). In the context of global warming, increasing the land's vegetation cover reduces the land's surface temperature to some extent (Alexander, 2021). This is illustrated by the use of green roofs (Chen, 2013). Appropriate campus plants reduce noise pollution on and off campus (Yang et al., 2010) and provide habitats for a variety of organisms (Guthula et al., 2022). Campus landscaping not only softens angular building forms but also serves as a focal point that improves the quality of vision (Yang et al., 2010). Moreover, as a resource for environmental education, diverse campus plants foster the cognitive and emotional growth of students (Harvey, 2010). Relevant studies have demonstrated the positive effects of campus

greening on the physical and mental development of students, as well as their academic outcomes (Huang et al., 2023). In addition to reducing health disparities caused by race, ethnicity, and socioeconomic status, campus landscaping promotes students' physical activity and mental health (Bikomeye & Beyer, 2021). Furthermore, how students interact with nature influences their mental health and environmental attitudes (Grabowska-Chenczke et al., 2022). Implementation of a well-designed campus greening initiative creates therapeutic natural environments that provide students with opportunities to engage in activities in natural environments, allowing them to overcome emotional distress and anxiety and improve their physical and mental health (Shin et al., 2023). Contact with green spaces reduces stress, boosts emotions, prevents depression, and improves a person's physical and mental health (Zhang et al., 2020). Different types of green landscapes provide participants with distinct therapeutic benefits (Zhang et al., 2022). Fun in natural environments shaped by campus plants promotes the physical and mental development of students, activates their sense of place, initiates their empathy for natural environments, and generates positive attitudes and behaviors (Mustapa et al., 2015). As they mature, children who are immersed in natural environments will develop stronger environmentalism attitudes, a connection to nature, and a sense of place. Engaging with natural environments through game-based approaches provides numerous health benefits and promotes positive environmental attitudes (Gill, 2014). The greening of campuses diversifies the types of games played in schools. Playing games in a way that is enjoyable, noncompetitive, and open-ended allows students of all ages, interests, sexes, and abilities to engage in physical activities (Dyment & Bell, 2008).

Native plant cultivation on campus yields numerous benefits. This study examines the status of campus plants in the Chiayi area, Taiwan, based on the proportion and distribution of native plants and the diversity of campus plants. The results are anticipated to serve as a future reference for campus greening solutions.

Materials and methods

Study region and sampling sites

This study's sample consisted of elementary schools in the central Taiwanese Chiayi area, including Chiayi County and city, which has an area of 1,963 km² and a difference in elevation of 4,000 m. The eastern portion of the nation is mountainous, while the western portion consists of plains and coastlines. Located in the Ficus-machilus zone, the expansive and level plains are a significant agricultural center. Due to the area's long history of development, however, there are

virtually no remaining virgin forests. The majority of the coastal region consists of low-lying alluvial plains. In the past, groundwater overexploitation for fish farming has caused land subsidence and water stagnation in certain regions (Tung & Hu, 2012). Seawater intrusion in coastal areas also contributes to coastal soil salinization (Liu et al., 2003). Because the Tropic of Cancer passes through it, Chiayi area is situated at the transition between subtropical and tropical zones. The area has distinct dry and wet seasons; in the summer there is abundant rainfall because the Central and Alishan mountain ranges block the southwesterly flow, whereas in the winter there is significantly less rainfall because the city is located on the lee side of the northeastern monsoon. Moreover, due to the large elevation difference, the climates of the plains and mountain regions are significantly different. Across Taiwan's coastal and mountain regions, schools are being constructed in various towns and cities, creating a microcosm of the island. According to the Taiwan Central Weather Bureau's monthly average temperature and precipitation statistics for Chiayi area from 1981 to 2010, the annual mean temperature was 23.1°C, the monthly average low was 16.5°C in January, the monthly average high was 28.6°C in July, and the annual average precipitation was 1,774.3 mm.

This study sampled schools based on the normalized difference vegetation index (NDVI). The NDVI reflects the condition of vegetation resources based on the absorption, transmission, and reflection of red and near-infrared light bands by plants. It is computed using the difference-sum ratio of near-infrared and visible light radiation. The NDVI can be used to differentiate between different types of vegetation, determine the growth status of the same type of plant, and precisely reflect the quality of plants growing in the vicinity of the sampling region. This study utilized July 2013 NDVI data derived from remote sensing for the Chiayi area. After arranging the data in ascending order and forming four quartiles, five schools were randomly selected from each group. The locations of the 20 elementary schools included in this study are depicted in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Distributions of the Chiayi area (Chiayi City and County) schools surveyed for this study.

Study region and sampling sites

We conducted campus plant surveys at each of the 20 elementary schools included in this study. The species of plants were recorded, but not their quantity. Non-identifiable plants were sampled and cross-checked afterward. Taxonomic information and scientific names were obtained from the Flora of Taiwan (Huang & Editorial Committee of the Flora of Taiwan, 2003). Once the species data was complete, classification and statistical analysis were executed. We also collected the names of plants that appear in elementary school textbooks, and checked whether these plants appeared in the campus, so as to facilitate the implementation of environmental education.

Data analysis

Analysis of the basic data

The survey results were presented in terms of the fundamental characteristics of the regions surveyed. We concentrated primarily on the distribution of campus plants, the proportion of native plants, and the dominant species. We used NTSYS-pc software for cluster analysis, calculated the intercluster distance using Euclidean distances, and plotted dendrograms using the unweighted pair group method analysis to examine the similarity of campus plants across various schools. We utilized SPSS 22.0 to compare the various school background factors. Pearson's correlation coefficient reflects the relationships between the types, quantities, and distributions of campus plants in various sampling regions. We compared the proportion of native plants, NDVI, the proportion of green spaces on campus, the plant species per unit area (100 m²), and the average

green space area per student (m^2 /person) using one-way ANOVA. The Scheffé test was utilized to conduct post-hoc comparisons.

Pteridophyte quotient analysis

The pteridophyte quotient (Ptp-Q) was proposed by Raunkiaer (1934) as an indicator of the dry and wet seasons. At the time of Raunkiaer's survey, there were 140,000 recognized phanerogam species in the world. Thus, Raunkiaer suggested comparing the proportion of pteridophytes in a given region to the global average. In this study, the Ptp-Q was calculated using the following formula, based on a catalog of the plants that were surveyed.

$$\text{Ptp-Q} = P \times 25 / S$$

where

P is the number of pteridophyte species

S is the number of phanerogam species (Huang & Editorial Committee of the Flora of Taiwan, 2003)

$$\text{Ptp-Q in Taiwan} = 565 \times 25 / 3577 = 3.9$$

Since the majority of pteridophytes thrive in humid and warm environments (van Konijnenburg-van Cittert, 2002), the Ptp-Q is greater in warmer and more humid regions. Arid and excessively cold regions with distinct wet and dry seasons are unfavorable for pteridophyte growth and reproduction, whereas warm and humid regions are ideal (van Konijnenburg-van Cittert, 2002). The Ptp-Q can be utilized to verify the distribution of pteridophytes and their relationship to the local climate.

Results

Diversity of campus plants

School structures in the sampling region

The fundamental characteristics of the 20 schools are listed in Table 1. There were seven schools in coastal regions with an elevation of less than 20 meters (referred to as the "Coast" zone), six in regions with an elevation between 20 and 150 meters (referred to as the "Hill" zone), and seven in mountain regions with an elevation exceeding 150 meters (referred to as the "Mountain" zone). There were five schools with an area less than 1 hectare, nine schools with an area between 1 and 2 hectares, and six schools with an area greater than 2 hectares. Seven schools had fewer than 60 students (designated as rural area schools), seven schools had 60 to 200 students (designated as general area schools), and six schools had more than 200 students (denoted as urban area schools).

Table 1. School structures in the sampling region (n=20).

Variable	Item	Frequency
School year of establishment	Less than 80 years ago	9
	80 to 95 ago	7
	More than 95 ago	4
Elevation	Below 20 m (Coast)	7
	20 to 150 m (Hill)	6
	Higher than 150 m (Mountain)	7
Campus area	Small (less than 1 ha)	5
	Medium (1 ha to 2 ha)	9
	Large (larger than 2 ha)	6
Student body size	Rural area (less than 60 students)	7
	General area (60 to 200 students)	7
	Urban area (more than 200 students)	6
Number of classes	Less than 7	11
	7 to 12	6
	More than 12	3

Types of campus plants and proportion of native vegetation

The plants grown in the 20 schools surveyed for this study are presented in Table 2. There were 150 families, 518 genera, and 770 species, including 98 pteridophytes, 21 gymnosperms, 506 dicotyledons, and 145 monocotyledons. The proportion of native plant species was 41.8% (322 types). The following are 30 endemic species: Taiwanese rain tree (*Koelreuteria henryi* Dummer), Fukugi tree (*Garcinia subelliptica* Champ.), Lanyu podocarp (*Podocarpus costalis* C. Presl), pseudocinnamomum (*Cinnamomum osmophloeum* Kaneh.), five-finger Taiwanese tongue fern (*Pyrrosia polydactyla* (Hance) Ching), Formosan cypress (*Chamaecyparis formosensis* Mastum.), Taitung cycad (*Cycas taitungensis* C. F. Shen, K. D. Hill, C. H. Tsou, & C. J. Chen), Botel Tobago cinnamon tree (*Cinnamomum kotoense* Kaneh & Sasaki), *Diplazium viridissimum* Christ, *Lepisorus monilisorus* (Hayata) Tagawa, Alishan mahonia (*Mahonia oiwakensis* Hayata), *Athyrium oppositipinnum* Hayata var. *pubescens* (Tagawa) Tagawa, *Dryopteris fructuosa* (Christ) C. Chr., Taiwan sunset fern (*Dryopteris lepidopoda* Hayata), *Polystichum mucronifolium* (Blume) Nayar & Kaur, *Polystichum parvipinnulum* Tagawa, *Lepisorus obscurevenulosus* (Hayata) Ching, *Pyrrosia matsudae* (Hayata) Tagawa, Taiwan cunninghamia (*Cunninghamia konishii* Hayata), Taiwan trident maple (*Acer buergerianum* Miq. var. *formosanum* (Hayata) Sasaki), *Machilus*

zuihoensis Hayata var. *zuihoensis*), green maple (*Acer serrulatum* Hayata), *Petasites formosanus* Kitam., *Cerastium fontanum* Baumg. var. *angustifolium* (M. Mizush.) H. Hara, Thinleaf elaeagnus (*Elaeagnus thunbergii* Serv.), Taiwan Azalea (*Rhododendron oldhamii* Maxim.), false-gold-flower rhododendron (*Rhododendron pseudochrysanthum* Hayata), *Syzygium formosanum* (Hayata) Mori, and yellow water lily (*Nuphar shimadae* Hayata). The average number of plant species per institution was 129.25, with 11.45 pteridophytes, four gymnosperms, 86.5 dicotyledons, and 27.3 monocotyledons. The proportion of native plants to total plants was 41,47% (**Error! Reference source not found.**).

Table 2. Cumulative campus plant resources in the sampling region.

	Families	Genera	Species
Pteridophytes	21	46	98
Gymnosperms	7	14	21
Dicotyledons	100	351	506
Monocotyledons	22	107	145
Total	150	518	770

Table 3. Campus plant statistics for every school in the region of study.

Sample	Plant classification					Native species	Ratio (native)	Ratio (textbook)
	Total	Pteridophytes	Gymnosperms	Dicotyledons	Monocotyledons			
Guogou (Coast 1)	107	2	4	75	26	45	42.06%	28.04%
Nanxing (Coast 2)	132	3	6	93	30	53	40.15%	30.30%
Budai (Coast 3)	124	4	6	81	33	52	41.96%	33.06%
Daxiang (Coast 4)	107	0	3	79	25	39	36.45%	31.78%
Gengliao (Coast 5)	74	0	4	53	17	28	37.84%	33.78%
Puzi (Coast 6)	120	2	6	84	28	41	34.17%	33.33%
Taibao (Coast 7)	143	1	4	95	43	49	34.27%	34.27%
Houtang (Hill 1)	165	3	5	119	38	43	26.06%	33.33%
Hexing (Hill 2)	92	2	0	73	17	32	34.78%	32.61%
Zhonglin (Hill 3)	113	1	4	77	31	36	31.86%	29.20%
Dingliu (Hill 4)	107	2	4	79	22	34	31.78%	35.51%
Wenya (Hill 5)	125	8	0	93	24	51	40.80%	32.00%
Zhuqi (Hill 6)	228	14	8	167	39	85	37.28%	24.56%
Dapu (Mount 1)	99	6	2	70	21	40	40.40%	41.41%
Dahu (Mount 2)	145	27	3	88	27	76	52.41%	28.28%
Laiji (Mount 3)	144	26	4	85	29	77	53.47%	30.56%
Ruili (Mount 4)	168	27	6	96	39	95	56.55%	25.60%
Taiping (Mount 5)	174	25	8	110	31	92	52.87%	29.31%

Sample	Plant classification					Native species	Ratio (native)	Ratio (textbook)
	Total	Pteridophytes	Gymnosperms	Dicotyledons	Monocotyledons			
Xiding (Mount 6)	123	35	0	70	18	68	55.28%	26.02%
Xianglin (Mount 7)	95	41	3	43	8	66	69.47%	12.63%
Mean	129.25	11.45	4	86.5	27.3	55.1	41.47%	30.28%

Dominant species on campus

Table 4 displays the frequency of campus plants in the sampling regions. 11 of the 20 most common plants were native species, excluding those that were introduced by humans: creeping woodsorrel (*Oxalis corniculata* L.), old world diamond-flower (*Hedyotis corymbosa* (L.) Lam.), Indian goosegrass (*Eleusine indica* (L.) Gaertn.), camphor tree (*Cinnamomum camphora* (L.) J. Presl. var. *camphora*), creeping tick trefoil (*Desmodium triflorum* (L.) DC.), skunk vine (*Paederia foetida* L.), orange jessamine (*Murraya exotica* L.), Chinese banyan (*Ficus microcarpa* L. f. var. *microcarpa*), Japanese lovegrass (*Eragrostis amabilis* (L.) Wight & Arn. ex Nees), bishop wood (*Bischofia javanica* Blume), and Irish poet tassel flower (*Emilia sonchifolia* (L.) DC. var. *javanica* (Burm. f.) Mattfeld). The top 20 most frequently occurring plants, including those planted by humans, were camphor tree (*Zamioculcas zamiifolia* (G. Lodd.) Engl.), Chinese juniper (*Juniperus chinensis* f. *Kaizuca*), orange jessamine, Chinese banyan, jungle flame (*Ixora williamsii* Sandwith), bishop wood, sweet osmanthus (*Osmanthus fragrans* (Thunb.) Lour.), golden dewdrop (*Duranta erecta* L.), Guiana chestnut (*Pachira aquatic* Aubl.), Garden croton (*Codiaeum variegatum* (L.) Rumph. ex A. Juss.), Taiwanese rain tree, lantana (*Lantana camara* L.), areca palm (*Dyopsis lutescens* (H. Wendl.) Beentje & J. Dransf.), great bougainvillea (*Bougainvillea spectabilis* Willd.), mango (*Mangifera indica* L.), frangipani (*Plumeria rubra* L.), dwarf umbrella tree (*Schefflera odorata* (Blanco) Merr. & Rolfe), pygmy water lily (*Nymphaea tetragona* Georgi), and bottle palm (*Hyophorbe lagenicaulis* (L. H. Bailey) H. The six native species were camphor, orange jessamine, bishop wood, Chinese banyan, Taiwanese rain tree, and dwarf umbrella tree. In terms of plant family, Asteraceae had the greatest number of species with 50, followed by Euphorbiaceae (37), Fabaceae (35), Poaceae (33), Araceae (20), Moraceae (20), Asparagaceae (17), Arecaceae (14), Rosaceae (16), Solanaceae (16), Rubiaceae (15), Lamiaceae (12), Malvaceae (11), Myrtaceae (11), Scrophulariaceae (11), Liliaceae (11), and Bignoniaceae (10). Despite being alien species, Araceae, Asparagaceae, Arecaceae, Liliaceae, and Bignoniaceae

were predominantly used as ornamental plants in horticulture. Therefore, we conclude that subjective preference for ornamental value has a substantial impact on the types of plants grown on campus.

Table 4. Statistics on dominant plant species at all schools in the study region.

Common name	Scientific name	Frequency
Creeping woodsorrel	<i>Oxalis corniculata</i>	17
Old world diamond-flower	<i>Hedyotis corymbosa</i>	17
Blanket grass	<i>Axonopus compressus</i>	17
Indian goosegrass	<i>Eleusine indica</i>	17
Asthma-plant	<i>Euphorbia hirta</i>	16
Camphor	<i>Cinnamomum camphora</i> var. <i>camphora</i>	16
ZZ plant	<i>Zamioculcas zamiifolia</i>	16
Chinese juniper	<i>Juniperus chinensis</i>	15
Romerillo	<i>Bidens pilosa</i> var. <i>radiata</i>	15
Creeping tick trefoil	<i>Desmodium triflorum</i>	15
Scarletfruit passionflower	<i>Passiflora foetida</i> var. <i>hispida</i>	15
Skunk vine	<i>Paederia foetida</i>	15
Orange jessamine	<i>Murraya exotica</i>	15
Chinese banyan	<i>Ficus microcarpa</i>	14
Jungle flame	<i>Ixora williamsii</i>	14
Japanese lovegrass	<i>Eragrostis amabilis</i>	14
Bishop wood	<i>Bischofia javanica</i>	13
Sweet osmanthus	<i>Osmanthus fragrans</i>	13
Golden dewdrop	<i>Duranta erecta</i>	13
Irish poet tassel flower	<i>Emilia sonchifolia</i> var. <i>javanica</i>	12
Guiana chestnut	<i>Pachira aquatic</i>	12
N/A	<i>Euphorbia makinoi</i>	12
Garden croton	<i>Codiaeum variegatum</i>	12
Taiwanese rain tree	<i>Koelreuteria henryi</i>	12
Lantana	<i>Lantana camara</i>	12
Areca palm	<i>Dyopsis lutescens</i>	12
Bermuda grass	<i>Cynodon dactylon</i>	12
Bird's-nest fern	<i>Asplenium nidus</i>	11
Mexican petunia	<i>Ruellia simplex</i>	11
False daisy	<i>Eclipta prostrata</i>	11
Oriental false hawksbeard	<i>Youngia japonica</i> subsp. <i>japonica</i>	11
Wrinkle-fruited leaf flower.	<i>Phyllanthus hookeri</i>	11
Paper mulberry	<i>Broussonetia papyrifera</i>	11
Great bougainvillea	<i>Bougainvillea spectabilis</i>	11

N/A: Not available

Feasibility of the curriculum incorporation of campus plants

In this survey, a total of 141 plants were mentioned in the natural science textbooks currently used in elementary and junior high schools. There were 41 species native to Taiwan, which accounted for 30%, while 114 species were planted by humans, which accounted for 80%. The top 13 most

frequently occurring plants are shown in Table 5, which include Indian goosegrass, creeping woodsorrel, camphor, orange jessamine, Chinese juniper, romerillo, Chinese banyan, bishop wood, Taiwanese rain tree, garden croton, lantana, areca palm, and Irish poet tassel flower. On average, each school had only 38.75 native species grown on campus that were mentioned in the textbooks.

Table 5. The frequency with which campus plants have been mentioned in textbooks.

Common name	Frequency	Common name	Frequency
Indian goosegrass	17	Oriental false hawksbeard	11
Creeping woodsorrel	17	Great bougainvillea	11
Camphor	16	Bird's-nest fern	11
Orange jessamine	15	Paper mulberry	11
Chinese juniper	15	Mango	10
Romerillo	15	Gale of the wind (chamber bitter)	10
Chinese banyan	14	Guava	10
Bishop wood	13	Pygmy water-lily	10
Taiwanese rain tree	12	Dwarf umbrella tree	10
Garden croton	12	Frangipani	10
Lantana	12	Indian almond	9
Areca palm	12	Bitter vine	9
Irish poet tassel flower	12	Taiwan sakura	9
Obscure morning glory	9	Sweet potato	8
Dooryard weed	9	Fishbone fern	8
Snake plant	9	Slender amaranth	8
Formosan gum	8	Blackboard tree	8
Chinese hibiscus	8	Madagascar periwinkle	8
Longan	8		

Examining the relationship between campus plants and regional climatic conditions

Composition of plant community

Figure 2 depicts the outcomes of the cluster analysis. Six schools in the Coast zone were initially clustered, and their phytological conditions were comparable. Then, six schools were clustered in the Mountain zone, followed by four schools in the Hill zone. Climate, environmental conditions, and elevation largely determined the regional distribution of plants on all campuses. In general, campuses closer to the Coast zone had lower species diversity, while the closer to the Hill zone and Mountain zone, the higher the species diversity. Campuses located in the Mountain zone generally had higher species diversity because these campuses were mostly located in more natural settings.

Figure 2. Dendrogram of the sampled schools' cluster analysis.

Analysis of species diversity of pteridophytes

Figure 3 depicts analysis results indicating that the mean Ptp-h-Q for all schools was 2.9. In the Mountain, Hill, and Coast zones, the Ptp-h-Q was 7.25, 0.84, and 0.36, respectively. Ptp-h-Q increased with altitude, indicating that mountainous regions are more conducive to pteridophyte growth than flatlands. Xianglin Elementary School (Mount 7) had the highest Ptp-h-Q at 19, while all schools in the Sea zone and a number of schools in the Hill zone had a Ptp-h-Q below 1. This indicates that few pteridophytes were discovered on the campuses of schools in flatlands.

Figure 3. Bar chart of each school's Ptp-h-Q.

Investigation of environmental factors

Relationship between campus green area and environmental factor

This study utilized Pearson's correlation coefficient to describe the relationships between campus size, elevation, proportion of native species, area of green spaces, student body size, species per unit area, and NDVI. The findings revealed that the majority of variables were significantly and strongly correlated ($p = 0.05$). The results of the Pearson correlation coefficient analysis are shown in Table 6. The correlation coefficient between elevation and proportion of native species was 0.92, indicating a positive relationship between campus elevation and proportion of native species. This may be a result of the lack of development in the areas surrounding schools located at higher altitudes. Moreover, environments with a greater proportion of pteridophytes are more likely to contain a greater proportion of native species. The correlation coefficient between the proportion of native species and the area of campus green spaces was -0.76, indicating that the number of native species decreases as campus green space area increases. Subjective preferences affect the status of campus plants, so this could be substantially influenced by human factors. The correlation coefficient between the number of species per unit area and the area of green spaces was -0.79, indicating that the number of plant species does not increase with a campus's green space area, thereby supporting the notion that campus environments are heavily influenced by human preferences. The correlation coefficient between the number of species per unit area and the total campus area was -0.734, indicating that schools with large campuses lacked a diversity of plant species. The correlation coefficient between the number of students and the area of green spaces was 0.65, indicating that green space planning takes into account the number of students. The correlation coefficient analysis between environmental factors indicates that campuses are heavily influenced by human intervention, as the variety of plant species grown on campuses is heavily influenced by administrators' personal preferences.

Table 6. Statistics of the correlation coefficients between the surveyed schools' variables.

Factor 1	Factor 2	Pearson's correlation coefficient	Significance (two-tailed)
Proportion of native plants	Elevation	0.704**	0.001
Proportion of native plants	Area of green spaces	-0.630**	0.003
Proportion of native plants	Number of species per unit area	0.548*	0.012
Number of species per unit area	Area of green spaces	-0.745**	0.000
Number of species per unit area	Total campus area	-0.734**	0.000
Student body size	Area of green spaces	0.655**	0.002
Student body size	Number of species	0.364	0.115
Elevation	Number of species per unit area	0.537*	0.015

Elevation	NDVI	0.406	0.076
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Note: * indicates a level of significance of $p < 0.05$, ** indicates a level of significance of $p < 0.01$, *** indicates a level of significance of $p < 0.001$.

We used one-way ANOVA to compare the proportion of native plants, NDVI, proportion of green spaces on campus, number of species per unit area (100 m^2), and mean green space area per student (m^2/person) in schools with varying elevations, campus areas, and locations (student body sizes). Table 7 provides the results. The results revealed significant differences between elevation and the proportion of native plants ($F = 21.917, p = 0.000$), the normalized difference vegetation index ($F = 11.93, p = 0.001$), and the number of species per unit area ($F = 16.61, p = 0.000$). Schools in the Mountain zone had a significantly greater proportion of native plants, NDVI, and number of species per unit area than schools in the Hill or Sea zones.

There were significant differences between campus area and the proportion of native plants ($F = 17.800, p = 0.040$), the proportion of green spaces ($F = 4.544, p = 0.026$), and the number of species per unit area ($F = 33.27, p = 0.000$). The results of the post-hoc analysis revealed that small schools had a significantly higher proportion of native plants and species per unit area than medium and large schools. Smaller schools had a greater proportion of green spaces than their larger counterparts. In terms of location (student body size), the results indicated that there were significant differences between the proportion of native plants ($F = 16.591, p = 0.020$) and the number of species per unit area ($F = 14.96, p = 0.000$). The results of a post-hoc analysis revealed that rural schools had a greater proportion of native plants and number of species per unit area than urban and general schools.

Table 7. Consolidated one-way ANOVA results of the schools in the sampling region.

		Classification by elevation (1) Coast (2) Hill (3) Mountain	Classification by campus area (1) Small (2) Medium (3) Large	Classification by student body size (1) Rural (2) General (3) Urban
Proportion of native plants	<i>F</i>	21.917*	17.800*	16.591*
	Scheffé post-hoc analysis	(3)>(2), (1)	(1)>(2), (3)	(1)>(2), (3)
NDVI	<i>F</i>	11.93*	2.522	3.37
	Scheffé post-hoc analysis	(3)>(1), (2) (2)>(1)		
	<i>F</i>	0.737	4.544*	1.021

		Classification by elevation (1) Coast (2) Hill (3) Mountain	Classification by campus area (1) Small (2) Medium (3) Large	Classification by student body size (1) Rural (2) General (3) Urban
Proportion of green spaces on campus	Scheffé post-hoc analysis		(1)>(2)	
Plant species per unit area	<i>F</i>	16.61*	33.27*	14.960*
	Scheffé post-hoc analysis	(3)>(1), (2)	(1)>(2), (3)	(1)>(2), (3)
Mean green space per student	<i>F</i>	0.165	3.663	2.244
	Scheffé post-hoc analysis			

Notes:

1. Classification by elevation: (1) Coast = below 20 m; (2) Hill = 20 to 150 m; (3) Mountain = Higher than 150 m
2. Classification by campus area: (1) Small = less than 1 ha; (2) Medium = 1 ha to 2 ha; (3) Large = larger than 2 ha
3. Classification by location (based on student body size):
(1) Rural area = less than 60 students; (2) General area = 60 to 200 students; (3) Urban area = more than 200 students
4. Level of significance at $p < 0.05$, expressed as *

Discussion

Increasing the proportion of native plant species to improve ecological systems and environmental education

Relevant studies have demonstrated the significance and benefits of campus plants (Harvey, 2010; Huang et al., 2023; Speake et al., 2013). Native plant planting improves the resilience of ecosystems. Nevertheless, our survey revealed that the average proportion of native campus plants was only 35.9%, whereas the proportion of alien plants was 64.0%. Numerous studies have demonstrated the ecological dangers of exotic plant species (Anderson & Crosby, 2018; Lowe et al., 2000; Pal et al., 2019). We propose that increasing the proportion of native campus plants and, consequently, the biodiversity provides enhanced ecosystem protection (Downing et al., 2012; Eisenhauer et al., 2011; Fornoff et al., 2019; Lüscher et al., 2022).

In addition, schools are ideal settings for environmental education because students can learn about and observe campus plants, and teachers can use the plants as onsite teaching materials. However, the average number of course-related plants mentioned in elementary and middle school textbooks (38.75) only covered 30.28% of campus plants. In other words, physical contact cannot be used to

learn about nearly 70% of the plants mentioned in textbooks. This information makes it easy for teachers to identify the campus plants mentioned in their lesson plans, thereby increasing the accessibility of their curriculum. Due to the small proportion of native plants on campus, however, the students lacked a deeper understanding of these species. This indicates that additional efforts are required to enhance the compatibility between campus environments and instructional materials. We propose that campus environments can be created by selecting native plants that thrive in the local environment, thereby increasing the robustness of ecosystems and the variety of campus plants that can be used as teaching tools.

Strengthening green spaces by enhancing management expertise

Numerous human and natural factors, such as subjective perceptions, differences in background knowledge, environmental restrictions, overall planning, maintenance, and management, management of invasive species, etc., influence the effectiveness of campus greening. The significance of subsequent maintenance and management cannot be overstated. Additionally, the types of plants grown on campus are heavily influenced by the preferences of administrators. Many schools have trees that have been improperly pruned or maintained. In order to create educational, ecologically sustainable, and aesthetically pleasing plant environments, tree planting on campus is merely a preliminary step that must be followed by long-term maintenance. Increasing management expertise, assigning dedicated personnel, establishing consultation services, and creating campus plant management manuals are additional methods for enhancing plant management.

The PtpH-Q is an effective tool for determining the phenological conditions of a campus

In addition to instrument-based measurements, the PtpH-Q is a more accurate indicator of the growth status of local plants. Our findings indicated that the PtpH-Q increased with altitude. This is due to the distinct rainy and dry seasons of Chiayi County, as well as the high salinity, strong winds, and long-term arid conditions of the coastal flatlands, which are all detrimental to the growth of pteridophytes. The PtpH-Q is an effective indicator for determining the phenological conditions of a campus based on the relative humidity and elevation conditions.

Conclusion

In general, only 36% of the campus plants grown in the elementary schools surveyed for this study were native plants, and the majority of the alien plants were ornamental. In addition, we found that schools with a high elevation, a small campus area, and a rural location had a significantly greater

proportion of native plants and number of plant species per unit area than schools with other elevations, campus areas, and locations. With increasing elevation and precipitation, the P_{tph-Q} increased. A disproportionately low proportion of native plants is not only detrimental to the environment and ecology, but also reduces students' opportunities to learn about native or endemic Taiwanese plants. Efforts should be made to gradually increase the proportion of native plants in the future, along with the incorporation of these plants into the curriculum, in order to enhance administrators' knowledge of campus plant management.

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